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IMPROVING MUTUAL COOPERATION OF STATE SYSTEM SERVICES IN EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

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Abstract: In this article, existing problems in the process of mutual cooperation of state system services in emergency situations are analyzed, measures to be implemented in order to achieve more coordinated and effective interdependence of these services and solutions aimed at improving the mutual cooperation of these services are recommended.

Keywords: state system services in emergency situations, emergency, helpful, cooperative, coordination, Integrated, operations, facilities, problem, coordination.

Emergency situations different from fields fast and coordinated actions Demand does, right planning and answer to give systems current will be done. Emergency situations important role who plays important from fields one Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system fire, vehicles and disaster technical are services. This services extraordinary situations during rescue operations, injured individuals transport and grass delete services display with is engaged in. However, extraordinary situations conditions Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system services display each is always stable process not because different offices to each other opposite role or to duties have to be can. That's why Emergency for of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of services mutually dependence increase, extraordinary to situations fast answer of giving efficient and own on time to be to provide need there is Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of services more coordinated and efficient to each other depending on reach for the following measures done increase to the goal according to:

1. Interagency Council : Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of different services from the representatives consists of interagency council organize joint answer to give strategies according to cooperation do, resources about data share to see and extraordinary situations during operations coordination.

2. Integrated communication system: different Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system services in the middle information in real time mode share to see opportunity Create for integrated contact system current to achieve That's all Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of services from the situation informed to be provides and answer actions from repetition keeps.

3. Mutual training: Various Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of services mutually study extraordinary to situations

answer givers of each other role and duties about main to understanding have to be provide . From this except this their extraordinary situations during answer to give actions coordination ability increases.

4.Joint exercises and Exercises: Various Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system services with participation joint training and training transfer, answer to give procedures to confirm, spaces or weaknesses to determine and common answer efficiency to increase help gives.

5.Standard operating Procedures : Various Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system services with participation joint operations for standard operational develop procedures (SOP). output, response to the givers guidance to be service does. Also SOP answer strategies coordinated and efficient extraordinary to situations answer of giving common to the goal suitable to come provides.

Emergency situations during public order , and road movement safety and fire safety, objects, territories, material and cultural riches protection to do provision of fires prevention to do and to delete about events organize reach and done increase, they with depends rescue their work done increase important importance occupation is enough.

Emergency situations Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of services mutually cooperation in their work the following problems available :

Limited of resources existence , that condition most of the time Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system services in the middle mutually cooperation to do obstacle does. For example, fast help cars lack of it while the injured in transportation to delays take coming can. This is har one first limited to resources to enter movement so different services between to the conflict take coming can.

Education of training enough that it is not, in this enough didn't happen study training extraordinary situations during Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of services ready not to be take coming can Together work and their actions coordination according to of training absence extraordinary to situations answer to give during disorder and to mistakes reason to be can.

Summary by doing in other words, Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system services in the middle mutual cooperation extraordinary to situations fast and efficient to work answer to give for is necessary. Limited enough resources level lack of training mutual cooperation for important difficulties gives birth. This issues solution to do Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of services extraordinary situations efficient cooperation provide for very important. To this different Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system services between mutually trust and coordination to the road to put according to integrated communication systems, combined trainings and standardized protocols and procedures current reach through reach can. Emergency situations unexpected at the time happen of people his life save to stay and property protection to do for fast coordinated the answer Demand does. Emergency situations during Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of services mutual dependence and efficiency increase for different offices in the middle coordination and cooperation to do very important. Interagency council done increase, Integrated contact system, cross-training, joint

training and training, standard operational procedures done increase extraordinary situations during Emergency of situations prevention get and such situations movement to do state system of services mutually cooperation to improve service does.

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